

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Dynamic relationship between Air pollution and Economic growth in Jordan: An Empirical Analysis

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Abstract

Apparently, throughout human history, pollution and the economy appear to have been inextricably linked. However, the relationship between environmental harm and economic development is complex, and disciplinary biases have splintered our understanding of it. This study applies Johansen cointegration which indicate that there exists a long-term relationship between air pollutants and economic growth. Multiple regression model indicates that there is a significant relationship between air pollution variables and the economic growth. The vector autoregressive model (Var) indicates a short run relationship between the variables. Then, Vector error correction model was fitted and the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) is supported. More so, the EKC shows that economic growth has both positive and negative significant impact on air pollution. Meanwhile, Granger causality test shows that economic growth has causal effect on air pollution. This indicates that Jordan has reduced CO₂ emissions along with other pollutants and thereby contributed to environmental improvement in the country.

Keywords: Air pollution, Environmental Kuznets curve (EKC), Cointegration test, Var model, VECM, Causality test, Multiple regression

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1.0 Introduction

There has been a lot of discussion in natural and social sciences about how pollution and economic development interact. The Environmental Kuznets curve has begun to blur some of the less obvious interrelationships between economic development and environmental outcomes (Ozokcu S, Ozdemir O, 2017). It is critical to consider the carrying capacity of the ecological system. Furthermore, many studies are conducted in narrow contexts, which prevents us from putting an integrated framework to the test. In order to advance towards a circularity, we must look at how to take advantage of pollution as a material asset in the products. Especially in the less developed countries, where pollution levels are increasing rapidly, government regulations often face the challenge of conflicting narratives on economic growth and human development. Meanwhile, without tighter

controls, air pollution emissions and concentrations are expected to rise rapidly, posing a serious threat to human health and the environment. The negative health effects of air pollution are expected to result in significant economic costs, with significant annual global welfare costs at the regional and sectoral levels (Jalil and Feridun, 2011). Furthermore, air pollution can harm trees and crop yields in a variety of ways (Rupakheti, 2015). Reduced crop and forest yields, reduced tree growth and survivability, and increased susceptibility to plant diseases, pests, and other stresses are all possible consequences of ground-level ozone (for instance, harsh weather). Jordan's government has made significant progress in its ability to reduce environmental degradation over the last decade.

This progress has been made possible by a stronger legislative framework, stronger institutions, and a number of publicly funded projects. The Ministry of Environment has accomplished the following since its inception